

NET-Fuels deliverable report

NET- Fuels | INCREASING BIOMASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY TO CARBON-NEGATIVE SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS BY COMBINATION OF THERMOCHEMICAL AND BIO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES

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Executive Summary

NET-Fuels is a Horizon Europe project running from 2022 to 2026, aimed at creating an innovative method for producing carbon-negative biofuels from low-value biogenic residues. This is achieved through an integrated approach combining thermochemical conversion, hydrogen separation from syngas, oxy-fuel combustion of tail gases, bio-electrochemical conversion of CO₂ into methane, and carbon sequestration in biochar. Additionally, NET-Fuels will produce a biofuel intermediate in the form of high-quality pyrolysis oil, which can be further refined into fuels.

As a Research and Innovation Action, the project aims to advance the integrated process to Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 5, laying the foundation for future demonstration and validation projects. The NET-Fuels initiative aims to produce 25 million tonnes of oil equivalent (Mtoe) of advanced biofuels by 2030, representing 7% of transportation fuel consumption, by utilizing approximately one-third to one-fourth of the available biogenic feedstock in Europe. Achieving this target is projected to result in a net reduction of 110 million tonnes of CO₂ emissions.

This document (Deliverable D3.1 on “*Report on construction, performance and optimization of BEM reactors*”) summarizes the work developed under NET-Fuels WP3 (*Bioelectrochemical process for CO₂ conversion to CH₄ from off-gas streams*), Task 3.1 (*Reactor design, construction and start-up*) and 3.2 (*BEM process optimization*) led by Leitac, in the period of 01/11/2022 to 31/10/2024 (M1-M24). Task 3.1 had as main objective the design of a BEM reactor based on a feasible and realistic scalable configuration and manufactured employing current industrial techniques. Task 3.2 had as main aim the BEM process optimization. Deliverable D3.1 mainly contains the outputs of the laboratory experimental campaign carried over during Tasks 3.1 and 3.2, and it is also particularly relevant for the work under development in WP3 tasks T3.3 (*Technology piloting with real gas effluents*) and T3.4 (*BEM operation and validation*). D3.1 has not only reported the completion of the work of task T3.1 and 3.2, but it also serves as means of verification for the achievement of NET-Fuels Milestone M3.1 (“*Laboratory BEM operation optimized in synthetic gas conditions*”).

1 Introduction

The primary objective of Work Package 3 (WP3) is to design, build, operate and optimize a Bio-Electrochemical Methanation (BEM) reactor for the bio-electrochemical conversion of CO₂ into CH₄. This process aims to valorize emissions from the Thermo-Catalytic Reforming (TCR) process, as outlined in WP2, with the overarching ambition of achieving a zero-emission process.

To meet this goal, WP3 has several specific objectives:

- O3.1 Design of a BEM reactor based on a feasible and realistic scalable configuration and manufactured employing current industrial techniques.
- O3.2 Laboratory testing and optimization.
- O3.3 Validating BEM process with real TCR gas and assessing microbial tolerance to impurities.
- O3.4 Providing the characteristics of all system relevant components for further process modelling.
- O3.5 Building a pilot BEM plant for direct integration with TCR and oxy-combustion processes.

This report summarizes the experimental activities conducted to address objectives O3.1, O3.2, and O3.4. The enhancement of BEM reactor performance required addressing several key technical aspects, including the optimization of electrode materials and geometry to increase active surface area and biofilm growth capacity, reduction of overpotentials within the system and optimization of reactor, improvement in the growth of hydrogenotrophic methanogens and their interaction with the cathode, and tuning of the operating conditions of the BEM reactor.

To achieve these goals, three double-chamber BEM reactors were designed and constructed at LEITAT for replicate experiments aimed at producing high-purity e-methane, and a control system was implemented in the laboratory-scale system. A schematic of the BEM reactor is reported in Figure 1. The optimization of reactor architecture involved several key developments, including the development of an efficient CO₂

dissolution system in the aqueous catholyte medium using hollow fiber membrane contactors (Figure 2), enhancement of cathodic performance for CH₄ production from dissolved CO₂, testing of various electrode materials, selecting a 3D-structured cathode material with an increased active surface area per unit of catholyte, minimizing internal resistance within the electrochemical system, and implementing an effective liquid-gas separation system to optimize CH₄ collection. A methanogenic biomass for rapid start-up of BEM has been developed and analyzed using 16S rRNA gene sequencing and quantitative PCR. Specific electrical tests were conducted to determine the kinetic behavior of the BEM reactor aimed at enhancing the conversion efficiency of CO₂ and electricity into CH₄, approaching biomethane standard quality with maximal current density demand.

Figure 1. Schematic of the BEM double-chambered reactor

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the hollow fibers membrane contactors for CO₂ solubilization in the electrolyte.

2 Screening of cathode electrode materials

Five materials that guarantee a 3D electrode with a high surface area were evaluated as electrode material for the development of the biocathode for e-methane production.

Specifically, two types of carbon brush electrodes (Mill-Rose, USA, and Tecnocepillo, Spain) and three metallic materials (titanium, Inconel, and stainless steel 316) were tested to elucidate their electrochemical behaviour under the process conditions of the BEM. The electrochemical analysis was conducted using a VMP3 Multichannel Potentiostat (Biologic, France) utilizing an Ag/AgCl reference electrode (NaCl 3M, +0.195 V vs SHE, Xi'an Yima Opto-electrical Technology, China) and titanium as counter electrode.

The materials were tested in a three-electrode configuration within a single-chamber electrochemical cell, where the working electrode (the material under examination), reference electrode, and counter electrode were all immersed in the same electrolyte. The electrolyte used was a mineral medium designed to support microbial growth, consisting of a 0.1 M phosphate buffer (PBS) supplemented with macronutrients and micronutrients. This medium was chosen based on prior experience with bioelectrochemical methanation processes, and its composition is reported in Annex 1. Cyclic voltammetry was conducted between 0.1 and -1.2 V to assess the hydrogen evolution capabilities of each material, with hydrogen serving as the intermediate product utilized by microbial biomass for methane production.

Figure 3 presents the maximum current densities for each material at -1.2 V, the potential at which the highest reducing current was observed for all materials. Stainless steel demonstrated the best performance, with more than double the current density achieved by Inconel mesh (the second best-performing material).

Figure 3. Current densities for each material at -1.2 V vs Ag/AgCl (maximum current densities achieved)

Among the various types of commercially available stainless steel, stainless steel wool INOX 434 (EN 1.4113) stands out as a 3D-structured material that offers both low cost and high electrical conductivity. This material has been successfully applied as a bioanode in bioelectrochemical systems, demonstrating good biocompatibility and the ability to promote the formation of highly active electroactive biofilms [1,2]. Figure 4 presents a photograph of the selected commercially available stainless steel wool 434, which was selected as the cathode material.

Figure 4. Photographic image of the stainless steel wool selected as material for biocathode development ([Stainless Steel Wool MEDIUM 150 gr | RAKSO \(ekksol.com\)](#))

3 CO₂ dissolution system in the aqueous catholyte medium

A commercially available liquid-gas membrane contactor, the 3M™ Liqui-Cel™ MM-1.7x5.5 with a membrane area of 0.5 m², was selected for CO₂ solubilization, targeting a treatment capacity of 50 L Day⁻¹. This membrane contactor was integrated into the laboratory setup and is planned for implementation in the pilot plant. Preliminary CO₂ solubilization tests were conducted under abiotic conditions, initially using distilled water and sodium hydroxide to increase pH and facilitate gas adsorption. In later stages, the medium was switched to the catholyte mineral medium used in the BEM system. The experiments were performed under the following conditions: pure CO₂ was supplied from a gas bottle at 1 barg and room temperature (25°C). The gas flow through the membrane contactor was set at 100 mL min⁻¹, while the liquid flow was maintained at 330 mL min⁻¹. The pH of the solution was monitored throughout, as CO₂ adsorption results in the acidification of the liquid phase. The uptake of gas in the liquid mixture was quantified by measuring the dissolved inorganic carbon using a Shimadzu TOC analyzer. The experimental results, reported in Figure 5, indicated a linear CO₂ solubilization rate of approximately 61.1 mL CO₂ m⁻² min⁻¹ in distilled water and NaOH. In contrast, the catholyte mineral medium exhibited an initial linear phase of faster CO₂ uptake at 127.2 mL CO₂ m⁻² min⁻¹. However, as the initial pH of 7.8 decreased to the carbonate-bicarbonate buffer value (pH 6.3), the adsorption rate rapidly declined until CO₂ absorption nearly ceased. At this saturation point, the catholyte mineral medium reached an inorganic carbon concentration of 400 ppm.

Figure 5. CO₂ solubilization in distilled water (left) and mineral medium (right)

4 Development of an active methanogenic biomass

A methanogenic biomass (inoculum) was enriched from samples collected from a sludge anaerobic digester at a local wastewater treatment plant in Terrassa, Spain. Three biological replicates (E1, E2, and E3) were incubated in the previously described mineral medium at 35°C under a gas phase consisting of 80% H₂ and 20% CO₂.

Liquid samples were collected at the start of incubation (T0) and after 10 days (T10) for analysis. The expression of **hdrA** and **mcrA** genes, which are critical for methanogenesis, was quantified using qPCR, while the V3-V4 regions of the 16S rRNA gene were sequenced to assess the microbial community composition.

The **hdrA** gene encodes a key enzyme essential for anaerobic respiration in methane-producing archaea [3]. The **mcrA** gene encodes the α subunit of methyl coenzyme M reductase, the enzyme responsible for catalyzing the final step in methanogenesis. The number of **mcrA** gene copies is significantly correlated with the methane production rate of the community. All known methanogens express this reductase, which plays a critical role in the final step of methane production [4].

4.1 Methodology

Specific primers and plasmids were designed using references from the literature, the NCBI BLAST database, and the GeneArt gene synthesis services (Thermo Fisher, Life Sciences) (see Table 1).

Table 1. Primer pairs selected for qPCR optimisation for methanogenesis, along with their respective primer sequences, amplicon sizes, melting temperatures (T_m) and references.

Primers	Primer sequences	T_m (°C)	Amplicon size	References
mcrA	F5'- CTTGAANNTCACTTCGGTGGNTC-3'	52.42	271 bp	[5]
	R5'- CGTTCATNGCGTAGTTNGGNTAGT-3'	52.69		
hdrA	F5'- CATCCCATTCCCAACARGCA-3'	55.21	183 bp	[3]
	R5'- GTTGGGTYGTATGGGTGTGT-3'	54.32		

All samples were collected under sterile conditions with sterile syringes, transferred into DNase-free Eppendorf tubes, and stored at -20°C. DNA was extracted using the ZymoBiomix Miniprep kit, and its quantity was measured with a Qubit Fluorometer (Invitrogen).

Quantitative PCRs were performed with Power Track Sybr Green Master Mix (Applied biosystems) on a QuantStudio 384w (Applied Biosystems) qPCR machine. All reactions, including standard curve dilutions, negative controls, blanks, and DNA samples, were performed in triplicate. Each reaction mixture contained 5 μ L of SYBR Green master mix, 4 μ L of plasmid or DNA, and 0.5 μ L of each primer pair at a concentration of 10 μ M, resulting in a final volume of 10 μ L per triplicate. qPCR data analysis involved calculating Ct values and gene copy numbers in Excel, with further statistical analysis and data visualization conducted in R Studio (Version 3.18). For DNA amplicon library preparation, the 16S rRNA gene V3-V4 regions (341F/R805) were targeted, and sequencing was performed using the Illumina MiSeq PE300 platform according to Illumina's guidelines. Sequencing was outsourced to Novogene (UK). Raw sequencing data were processed with QIIME2 (Version 2022.11), and Amplicon Sequence Variant (ASV) assignment was completed using the DADA2 algorithm. Taxonomic classification was achieved at 99% similarity using the q2-feature-classifier plugin with the SILVA 132 database. The optical density measured at a wavelength of 600 nm (OD₆₀₀) is a measure of the turbidity or cloudiness of a liquid culture, commonly used in microbiology to estimate the concentration of cells in a suspension. A higher OD₆₀₀ value generally indicates a higher concentration of cells. The OD₆₀₀ of the liquid samples (~1 mL) was determined by measuring absorbance at 600 nm with a Hach DR 3900 spectrophotometer. Gas composition (CH₄, CO₂, H₂, O₂ and N₂) was quantified using a gas chromatograph (490 Micro GC Natural Gas Analyzer, Agilent, Spain) equipped with a dual channel cabinet and a thermal conductivity detector. Channel 1, which used argon as the carrier gas, was equipped with a 10-meter CP-Molsieve 5A column and was used for separating and analysing the permanent gases H₂, O₂, N₂, and CH₄. Channel 2, which used helium as the carrier gas, contained a CP-PoraPlot U column and was used to separate hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) and CO₂.

4.2 Results of microbiological analysis on the inoculum

The biological replicates E2 and E3 demonstrated a high rate of substrate consumption, leading to significant methane production. For E2, the final methane volumetric composition was 45.34% (± 0.69), while for E3, it was 32.35% (± 0.38). In contrast, E1 did not produce any methane and exhibited negligible substrate consumption. Consistent with these observations, copies of the *mcrA* and *hdrA* genes, indicative of methanogenic archaea, were detected in all samples from E2 and E3 but were absent in E1. Consequently, E1 was excluded from further analysis.

The gene copies of *mcrA* and *hdrA* in E2 did not exhibit significant changes between T0 (*mcrA*: 110610; *hdrA*: 25837) and T10 (*mcrA*: 159829; *hdrA*: 19562), suggesting that methanogenic archaea containing these genes were already abundant at the start of the trials. In contrast, the E3 culture showed a significant increase in gene copies from T0 to T10. Initial copy numbers at T0 (*mcrA*: 11; *hdrA*: 38) increased markedly by T10 (*mcrA*: 25477; *hdrA*: 7030). This increase likely indicates that, although the initial culture had a low abundance of these genes, the microbial communities expanded over time, resulting in a higher presence of archaea carrying the *mcrA* and *hdrA* genes. This rise in gene copies corresponds with the observed growth of the methanogenic culture, as evidenced by the increase in OD₆₀₀ over the two-week period. By the end of the experiment, both methanogenic cultures had an OD₆₀₀ value of approximately 0.5 to 0.6.

The microbiome analysis focused initially on the ratio between bacteria and archaea, as shown in Figure 6. In the E2 samples, archaea were dominant, with a relatively high abundance observed at both T0 (31%) and T10 (40%). Conversely, in the E3 samples, the relative abundance of archaea increased from T0 (0.3%) to T10 (7%). This trend correlates with the earlier qPCR results, where E2 exhibited a consistently high number of gene copies, while E3 showed a time-dependent increase in methanogenic archaea and corresponding gene copies.

The analysis of the archaea composition at the genus level across all samples and time points, reported in Figure 7, revealed that *Methanobrevibacter* was predominant. *Methanobrevibacter* is a hydrogenotrophic methanogen, capable of utilizing hydrogen and carbon dioxide to produce methane [6]. Another significant genus identified was *Methanobacterium*, which is also involved in hydrogenotrophic methane production but can utilize a broader range of substrates, including H₂, CO₂, formate, and alcohols [7].

Both *Methanobacterium* and *Methanobrevibacter* are essential for methane production, and previous research has shown that their presence in inoculums enhances methane yield [6]. Consequently, their presence, along with the high expression of *mcrA* and *hdrA* genes, indicates the successful establishment of an active methanogenic community. Based on the overall results, it can be concluded that, regardless of the initial "activation state" of a biological inoculum, the developed cultivation protocol effectively ensures the activation of genes involved in methanogenesis and the selection of hydrogenotrophic methanogens, resulting in a highly effective methanogenic inoculum.

The developed methanogenic biomass was maintained incubated in the previously described mineral medium at 35°C under agitation. The maintenance substrate consisted of a gas phase containing 80% H₂ and 20% CO₂, stored in multi-layered gas bags. Given that the production of 1 mole of methane requires the consumption of 1 mole of CO₂ and 4 moles of H₂, methane production leads to a decrease in the gas bag volume. Consequently, the gas bags were exchanged when their volume reached approximately 20% of the initial volume, and they were then refilled with the same gas mixture.

Figure 6. Bar plot at log₁₀ of genes *hdrA* (A) and *mcrA* (B) involved in methanogenesis at T₀ and T₁₀ in the two replicates (E2 and E3)

Figure 7. Composition plot of sequencing data from 16srRNA of methanogenic cultures. (a) Composition at Kingdom level of all samples. (b) Subset of archaeas at genus level.

5 Construction, testing and start-up of laboratory scale BEM reactors

5.1 Laboratory system description

Three double-chambered 14x14 cm BEM reactors were designed and constructed, each one with a chamber open area of 11x11 cm, with a compartment volume of 250 mL. A photo of the open cell is provided in Figure 8. The cathode, with a geometrical surface area of 121 cm², was packed with stainless steel wool (RAKSO Stainless Steel Wool Medium INOX 434, RAKSO, Germany). A 6 mm diameter titanium rod (GoodFellow, UK) served as the electrical connection to the external power source. The anode electrode consisted of a 3x3 cm titanium mesh coated with 12 g m⁻² Ir-*MMO* (Magneto, The Netherlands), providing a geometrical electrode area of 9 cm². This electrode was soldered to a 6 mm diameter titanium rod. An Ag/AgCl reference electrode (+195 mV vs SHE) was inserted into each compartment. The three BEM reactors were powered by individual power sources (TENMA 72–2715, Farnell, Spain), with the negative terminals connected to the cathodes and the positive terminals to the anodes. The reactors operated in galvanostatic mode, ensuring a constant current flow through the individual cells (0–35 A m⁻² [8]). Cell voltages for the three BEM units were recorded using a PicoLog 1012 data acquisition board (Farnell, Spain), while single electrode potentials against the reference electrode were recorded using a National Instrument acquisition board (NI-USB 6212, National Instruments, Spain), using the DAQexpress acquisition software. Two types of ion exchange membrane, a cation exchange membrane (CEM) (RALEX, MemBrain s.r.o., Czech Republic) and a bipolar membrane (BPM) (RALEX, MemBrain s.r.o., Czech Republic) were evaluated as separator between compartments.

Figure 8. Photographic picture of the open BEM cell

A CEM allows protons (H^+ ions) and other cations to pass through preferentially, while reducing the migration of anions. With this separator, an acidic anolyte is typically required, as it provides a source of protons that can migrate through the CEM to the cathode, where they participate in the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). Using an acid with increased concentration (molarity) on the anode side helps maintain a high proton concentration, which is crucial for the efficient operation of the system. Insufficient proton availability can compromise electron transfer efficiency and overall system performance. However, using higher acid concentrations, particularly under oxidative conditions, can damage the metallic anode materials, potentially reducing their operational lifetime. Additionally, the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) is more favorable in alkaline conditions, presenting a higher overpotential in acidic environments, which could further impact the efficiency and durability of the system. A BPM consists of two layers of different ion-exchange materials: an anion exchange layer and a cation exchange layer. When an electric current is applied, water molecules dissociate into H^+ and hydroxide ions (OH^-) at the interface between the two layers. The H^+ ions migrate to the cathode while the OH^- ions migrate to the anode. This process effectively balances proton consumption at the cathode and proton production at the anode without net ion movement between the two compartments. The use of a BPM therefore allows to use an alkaline electrolyte, more favourable towards OER compared to acid, at the anode. Figure 9 report a schematic of the working principle for both separators.

Figure 9. Schematic of the ion movements for the cation exchange membrane (CEM) and the bipolar membrane (BPM)

The anolyte was continuously recirculated at a rate of 200 mL/min using a peristaltic pump (HF-Lab, Hygiaflex, Spain) through a 2 L Schott bottle, where the produced oxygen was separated. A pH control unit (TPR 603, Tekna Evo), consisting of a pH probe and a dosing pump, was integrated into the anolyte recirculation loop to continuously monitor the pH level. The anolyte circuit was maintained at an overpressure of 180 mbar by a non-return valve located in the oxygen outflow line, which opens at this pressure. Line pressure was monitored with a digital pressure indicator (PS42, E-MC). Oxygen production was quantified using a flowmeter (BlueVCount, BlueSens, Germany) and logged onto a computer via BlueVis software (BlueSens, Germany). The previously described mineral medium has been used as catholyte and was recirculated at a rate of 200 mL/min using a peristaltic pump (Hygiaflex) through a 5 L Schott bottle, where the gas outflow was separated from the liquid phase. A dissolved CO₂ sensor (InPro5000i, Mettler Toledo, Spain) was integrated into the catholyte recirculation line to measure the CO₂ concentration, with data logged by an M400 datalogger terminal (Mettler Toledo, Spain). A pH control unit, equal to that in the anolyte loop, was also present. The catholyte temperature was regulated to 35°C using a thermostat (Huber) connected to a plate-exchange heater (Hrale B3-12-30, Ningbo Hrale Plate Heat Exchanger Co., Ltd., China). The thermostat was connected to an external temperature probe inserted in the catholyte circuit, which adjusts the heating water temperature to maintain the setpoint. CO₂ inflow was controlled by a mass flow controller (MFC D-6411, Iberfluid, Spain), with CO₂ being sparged into the medium. The CO₂ supply was manually activated when dissolved CO₂ fell below 50% of its solubility limit and was stopped when it exceeded 100%. The catholyte circuit, like the anolyte, was kept at an overpressure of 180 mbar via a non-return valve in the gas outflow line, with pressure monitored by the same digital indicator as the anolyte circuit. The produced gas was quantified by a flowmeter (BlueVCount, BlueSens, Germany) and logged using BlueVis software (BlueSens, Germany). Methane and CO₂ concentrations in the gas outflow were measured with two BCP infrared sensors (BlueSens, Germany), with data recorded using the same software. A schematic of the laboratory setup is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Schematics of the laboratory scale BEM unit

5.2 Selection of separator, anolyte and anode material

To identify the optimal membrane, anolyte medium and anode material for the BEM reactor, various combinations of these components were tested and evaluated in the laboratory setup. The tests were performed in the BEM reactors performing abiotic water splitting (hydrogen evolution at the cathode and oxygen evolution at the anode). Linear sweep voltammetry was conducted within the current density range of 0 to 33 A/m² (33 A m⁻² corresponding to the potentiostat maximum current output of 400 mA). This range was selected based on findings by Liu *et al.* [8], who observed increased methane production as the current density of the system increased from 5 to 35 A/m².

Initially, the CEM previously mentioned was used with an acidic electrolyte (0.001 M H₂SO₄) and an Ir-MMO anode. As previously explained, the acidic anolyte was chosen to prevent non-selective cation crossover, as protons were the only cations present. MMO was selected for its acid resistance and status as the leading anode material for oxygen evolution reactions in abiotic electrolyzers. However, this combination proved unsuitable, resulting in overpotentials exceeding 7 V at a current density of 10 A m⁻². The observed effects can be attributed to the use of a highly dilute acidic electrolyte (0.001 M H₂SO₄), which resulted in low ionic conductivity, thereby increasing ohmic losses. The OER is inherently associated with a high intrinsic overpotential, particularly in acidic environments, necessitating a significant overpotential to achieve the desired current density. This challenge is further aggravated when the electrolyte is suboptimal, such as when proton availability is low, or solution resistance is high. However, while using more concentrated acids could potentially improve performance, it also poses risks to the stability of MMO. Despite being the most resistant OER catalysts in acidic environments, MMO are still metal-based materials and, as such, are vulnerable to corrosion under acidic conditions, especially when subjected to oxidative potentials.

Due to the problems associated with use of CEM and acid anolyte, a second experiment was performed using the BPM previously described. Unlike CEM, BPM does not permit direct transport of species between compartments; instead, it operates via water ionization to balance ion movement. MMO, stainless steel 304 mesh (SSM), and Nickel mesh (NiM) were tested as anodes in a 7 M KOH anolyte, the industrial standard for alkaline electrolyzers. At this concentration, all anodes exhibited similar overpotentials, with a total cell voltage around 1.5 V at 10 A m⁻², as shown in Figure 11. In the third experiment, the anolyte was replaced with the catholyte medium, to test the effect of a less alkaline (and therefore less aggressive) electrolyte on the process performance. Also, for the system implementation prospective, it would be useful to limit the amount of chemical medium utilized. The results are also presented in Figure 11. In this setup, the MMO anode showed a significant increase in both anode potential and BPM overpotential, leading to a cell voltage of 4.7 V at 10 A m⁻². Conversely, NiM and SSM anodes exhibited only a modest increase in anode potential, from 0.5 V to 1.1 V at 10 A m⁻², resulting in a total cell voltage of 2.8–2.9 V, of which 0.7–0.8 V was attributed to BPM overpotential. From the presented results, it appears that the use of a BPM together with an alkaline electrolyte, ensures the lowest internal resistance of the electrochemical system. This results in a lower cell voltage and, consequently, reduced energy demand for the system. Under these conditions, SSM and NiM have shown promising results in short-term experiments. However, their long-term stability under process conditions is a crucial requirement for their successful application in the system.

Figure 11. Comparison of electrochemical performance across different electrode materials and electrolytes. The graphs show the relationship between potential (V) and current density ($A\ m^{-2}$) for mixed metal oxides, nickel mesh, and stainless steel 304 mesh electrodes in 7M KOH (left column) and catholyte media (right column). Key parameters measured include cell voltage (red), anode potential (black), cathode potential (blue), and separator (BPM) overpotential (green).

The long-term stability of the SSM and NiM were tested in two BEM cells, operated as electrolyzers (abiotic water splitting) utilizing KOH 7 M as anolyte, at a current density of $33\ A\ m^{-2}$ over the course of a week, maintaining the overpotentials reported in Figure 11. This operative current density was chosen for simulating a high-demanding BEM, allowing for the early identification of potential failure mechanisms in the anodes. Afterwards, the cells were opened, and the anodes were visually inspected. As shown in Figure 12, SSM presented severe corrosion, up to partial dissolution, in our operative conditions. As presented in Figure 13, also NiM showed signs of pitting corrosion in our conditions, with the formation of nickel salts.

Both SSM and NiM exhibited good electrochemical performance in short-term tests; however, they were unsuitable for long-term operation under our conditions. The likely cause of corrosion in these materials is the presence of ions such as chloride and sulphate in the anolyte, which are known to accelerate metal corrosion by forming metal salts like nickel and iron chlorides. These ions likely originated from co-ion leakage across the bipolar membrane from the catholyte, which, as reported in Annex 1, is rich in various ions necessary for microbial growth. As a result, MMO electrodes were selected as the anode material for BEM operation, with BPM as the separator material, and KOH 1M as the anolyte. The KOH concentration was reduced from 7M to 1M to minimize co-ion leakage, due to the high levels of potassium and hydroxide ions in the anolyte, and to decrease the electrolyte's aggressiveness, which could increase the risk of failure of the system components (i.e. peristaltic tubing, connectors, etc.).

Figure 12. Photographic images of the stainless-steel mesh electrode after 1 week of operation as anode for oxygen evolution at a current density of 33 A m^{-2}

Figure 13. Photographic images of the nickel mesh electrode after 1 week of operation as anode for oxygen evolution at a current density of 33 A m^{-2} .

5.3 Biocathode start-up

5.3.1 Experimental run with bipolar membrane

The biocathodes of the three BEM cells were inoculated with 2.5 L of the previously described methanogenic inoculum. The cells were galvanostatically controlled at a fixed current density of 5 A m^{-2} , which was chosen as inoculation current density based on literature [8]. The catholyte consisted of the previously described mineral medium, with an initial pH of 7.04 and a starting conductivity of 8.28 mS cm^{-1} . The anolyte was 1 M KOH, with an initial pH of 14. The two compartments were separated by the previously described BPM. CO_2 was provided to the system as previously described, aiming at maintaining a 50-100% saturation range. After 4 days of operation, the catholyte pH increased to 10.74, as reported in Figure 14. Simultaneously, an osmotic imbalance occurred, with approximately 100 mL of anolyte transported to the cathode compartment through the BPM due to osmosis. To counteract the excessive alkalinization caused, the anolyte was replaced with a 0.1 M phosphate buffer (PBS) on day 7. Despite this adjustment, the issue persisted, and the catholyte pH rose to 9.48. This pH increase was likely due to co-ion leakage through the BPM at low operating current densities. BPMs require a minimum current density to function effectively, as they are prone to co-ion leakage under suboptimal conditions. Sun et al. [9] investigated a solar-driven water-splitting cell equipped with a BPM, using 0.5 M aqueous potassium borate as the anolyte and 1.0 M H_2SO_4 as the catholyte. They reported that at a current density of 5 A m^{-2} , 70-90% of the current facilitated water dissociation, while the

remaining was lost due to co-ion crossover. This suggests that under our operating conditions, significant co-ion leakage occurred, leading to the BPM's failure to maintain pH balance between compartments.

Figure 15 presents the potentials of each component of the BEM unit, expressed as the average potential across the three BEM cells. The anode potential gradually increased over time, rising from 0.5 V on day 0 to 2.35 V by day 6. In contrast, the cathode potential remained relatively stable at approximately -1 V. The total cell voltage experienced a rapid increase, stabilizing around 4 V by day 5. The separator overpotential exhibited minimal variation throughout the experiment, maintaining a value close to 0.6 V. The switch to PBS as the anolyte led to a decrease in anode potential, and consequently, the cell voltage dropped by approximately 0.3 V. In conclusion, the BPM proved unsuitable as a separator in our system due to the insufficient current density. For this reason, the BPM was replaced with a CEM, whose ion-exchange performance is independent of the system's current density. Although the CEM exhibited higher overpotentials during short-term electrochemical tests, the achieved results showed that the BPM only provided low internal resistance of the system during short-term trial, while the anodic overpotential rapidly increased during longer term trials, leading to a corresponding rise in cell voltage.

Figure 14. Catholyte pH trend in time

Figure 15. Average potentials of each cell component over the 8-day period. The graph depicts the potential changes of the anode, cathode, ΔE cell, and separator overpotential, measured in volts (V).

5.3.2 Experimental run with cation exchange membrane

The three BEM reactors were started as outlined in the previous section, with the only modification being the use of a CEM as the separator and 0.1 M PBS as the anolyte. After just two days of operation, the PBS buffer was broken, causing the pH to drop to 2.27. Subsequently, the anolyte pH stabilized around 2, while the cathode pH remained between 7 and 8 (Figure 16). After 40 days, the anolyte was replaced with 1 M phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4) (conductivity 80 mS cm^{-1}) to assess the impact of a concentrated acid with ten times the conductivity of 0.1 M PBS on the system's internal resistance. The following day, the catholyte pH sharply decreased to 2, likely due to the excessive proton transport through the CEM by diffusion. As a result, the system was reinoculated, and the anolyte was reverted to 0.1 M PBS buffer.

The non-selective ion transport of the CEM, which allows cations other than protons to pass, appears to prevent excessive acidification of the catholyte, thereby helping maintain a neutral pH. Potassium ion transport reduces net proton transfer, mitigating acidification, while CO_2 feeding also helps balance the medium's alkalinity.

During the first 40 days, the anolyte conductivity remained stable between 7.75 and 8 mS cm^{-1} . However, after using H_3PO_4 as the anolyte and subsequently switching back to PBS, the anolyte conductivity rose to 15 mS cm^{-1} before quickly stabilizing at 10 mS cm^{-1} . The cathode conductivity showed variability, likely due to fluctuations in dissolved CO_2 levels at the time of sampling (Figure 16). For the first 40 days, the cathode conductivity oscillated around 17.5 mS cm^{-1} . Following reinoculation, which involved a complete exchange of cathode and anode media, the initial conductivity dropped to 10 mS cm^{-1} , then rapidly increased to 20 mS cm^{-1} , eventually reaching 23 mS cm^{-1} .

Figure 16. Time-course profiles of (a) pH and (b) conductivity in the cathode and anode chambers.

Figure 17 illustrates the average potential of the cells and their single components over the course of the experimental run. Throughout most of the experiment, the cell potential remained relatively stable, ranging between 2.5 and 3.8 V. However, a notable decrease occurred around day 40, coinciding with the

introduction of 1 M phosphoric acid as the anolyte. This change led to a temporary reduction in cell potential, primarily due to a decrease in anode potential, which resulted from the higher conductivity of the phosphoric acid compared to the PBS. The anode potential stabilized between 1.5 and 2.0 V, while the cathode potential consistently remained at -1.0 V throughout the experiment. The overall system overpotential, largely attributed to pH imbalance and liquid resistance [10], accounted for only 0.1 to 0.3 V.

Figure 17. Triplicate average potential (V) versus time (days) for different components of the BEM. The graph shows the mean potential trends for the overall cell (red), anode (black), cell overpotential (green), and cathode (blue). Significant events include the replacement of the anolyte with 1 M phosphoric acid on day 40, leading to observable changes in potential values, particularly in the cell and anode potentials.

Figure 18 depicts the gas composition profiles over time for two outputs: E-methane gas (Figure 18a) and anode outflow gas (Figure 18b). Both gasses were analyzed using the gas-chromatography methodology illustrated in Section 4.1.

Initially, the e-methane gas consists primarily of CO_2 , with 10% unreacted H_2 . Over time, there is a significant increase in CH_4 concentration, while CO_2 levels decrease, eventually reaching 66% methane and 29% CO_2 , with no remaining unreacted hydrogen. This shift indicates a successful conversion of CO_2 to CH_4 , likely driven by the proliferation of hydrogenotrophic methanogens and their enhanced methane production. The e-methane sample on day 42 was taken one day after re-inoculation, therefore presenting unreacted H_2 and lower amount of CH_4 . However, there was a rapid rise in methane concentration, reaching a concentration of 73.9 % by day 54, demonstrating the high activity of the developed methanogenic inoculum.

In the anolyte outflow, oxygen is the main component, reaching a purity of up to 95 %. The primary impurity is CO_2 , which cross over from the catholyte. This contamination occurs because the CEM is porous, allowing gases to permeate through the membrane pores. Figure 19 shows the trends of CO_2 and CH_4 content measured at the BEM cathodic outflow using BCP sensors, alongside the dissolved CO_2 levels in the liquid phase. The data reveal a strong correlation between the dissolved CO_2 in the catholyte and the percentage of CO_2 present in the gaseous outflow. Methane is consistently present in concentrations around 70 % when the dissolved CO_2 falls below 30 %. These findings suggest that to enhance methane content in the outflow, it would be beneficial to limit dissolved CO_2 between 20-40%, thereby reducing excessive CO_2 desorption and minimizing contamination of the produced methane.

Figure 18. Gas composition profiles over time for (a) E-methane gas and (b) anode outflow gas. The compositions are shown as percentages of O₂ (red), N₂ (orange), H₂ (blue), CH₄ (yellow), and CO₂ (green) at various time points (in days).

Figure 19. Gas composition profiles over time, showing the content of CH₄ (methane), CO₂ (carbon dioxide) in the outflow, together with the trend of dissolved CO₂ in the system.

Figure 20 illustrates the fluctuations in ion concentrations within the catholyte during the experimental period. The anions were quantified using an ionic chromatograph (ICS-3000, Dionex, Spain) while the cations were quantified by the means of Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (AGILENT 8900 ICP-QQQ, Agilent Technologies, Spain). Notably, potassium (K^+) and phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) showed significant variations, with a sharp decline in K^+ concentration around day 40, attributed to the replacement of the catholyte medium. Following this, the transport of potassium through the CEM led to a marked increase in its concentration, returning to levels observed before the anolyte change. On the other hand, following the exchange of catholyte medium the PO_4^{3-} concentration increased dramatically, up to 9.5 g L^{-1} . This effect was due to phosphate diffusion from the anode side, driven by the high concentration gradient between the two compartments. It is important to note that while the CEM facilitates the movement of positively charged ions, it does not completely prevent the passage of anions. The concentrations of sodium (Na^+), chloride (Cl^-), sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), and calcium (Ca^{2+}) remained relatively stable throughout the experiment.

Figure 20. Concentration profiles of Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Mg^{2+} in the catholyte over time.

Figure 21 illustrates the fluctuations in ion concentrations within the anolyte over the course of the experiment. The concentration of chloride ions (Cl^-) increased rapidly from 50 mg/L to 150 mg/L during the first 20 days. A similar rise occurred after day 40, following the replacement of the anolyte. In contrast, magnesium (Mg^{2+}) and sulphate (SO_4^{2-}) remained at minimal levels throughout the experiment, with no significant changes. Calcium (Ca^{2+}) displayed inconsistent behaviour but showed a marked increase after reinoculation on day 40. Potassium (K^+), phosphate (PO_4^{3-}), and sodium (Na^+) exhibited similar trends, with gradual decreases until day 40. After reinoculation, the concentrations of these ions steadily declined, corresponding to their increase in the catholyte due to crossover through the CEM, driven by the concentration gradient between the compartments.

Figure 21. Concentration profiles of various ions in the anolyte over time. The upper panel displays the concentrations of Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , Ca^{2+} , and Mg^{2+} , the bottom panel presents the concentrations of PO_4^{3-} , K^+ , and Na^+ .

5.3.3 qPCR tracking of gene expression

Quantitative PCR (qPCR) targeting methanogenesis-related genes was conducted to quantify the expression of methanogenic genes in the catholyte's liquid bulk during the start-up and operation of the bioelectrochemical system. Additionally, biomass samples used for inoculating the laboratory setup were collected at the beginning of the experiment (E1_IN, E2_IN, and E3_IN) and after 82 days (E1_FIN, E2_FIN, and E3_FIN) to assess the stability of the methanogenic culture over time.

The targeted methanogenic genes were *hdrA* and *mcrA*, using the methodology described in Section 6. Primer selection and plasmid design incorporating the selected primers were followed by qPCR optimization to evaluate the specificity and sensitivity of each primer. Specifically, we assessed the primers' ability to amplify the intended target region and the range of detectable quantities. Calibration curves were used to quantify gene copy numbers by correlating them with sample volume. Cycle threshold (CT) values, representing the point at which amplification is detected, showed an inverse relationship with the amount of target nucleic acid in the sample. The quantity of each sample was determined using the standard curve and expressed relative to the calibration.

To ensure accuracy and validate amplification specificity, blanks and negative controls were included in the assay. The negative controls consisted of bacterial samples from *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, which lack the targeted genes and therefore served as appropriate controls for qPCR.

Table 2 details the temperatures, times, and cycles for pre-incubation, amplification, and melting curve steps. Trials were conducted to optimize the annealing temperature and primer concentration.

Table 2. qPCR set up for methanogen and EET primers respectively. Temperatures, times, and cycles for the steps from pre-incubation, amplification and melting curve are shown.

Step	Temperature(°C)	Time	Cycles	Primers
Pre-incubation	95	5 min.	1	mcrA and hdrA
Denaturation	95	10 sec.	35	
Annealing	60	1 min.	35	
Extension	72	10 sec.	35	
Melt Curve - Step 1	95	5 sec.	1	
Melt Curve - Step 2	60	1 min.	1	
Melt Curve - Step 3	95	-	1	

The optimal annealing temperature for the primers was empirically determined to be 60°C. A standard curve was generated by plotting CT values against copy numbers from a series of 10-fold dilutions of a plasmid containing the target sequence. This analysis identified a linear range for quantification, spanning CT values from 28 to 4.1, corresponding to copy numbers ranging from 10⁸ to 10². Based on these results, standard curve equations for each primer were derived, allowing for precise calculation of copy numbers in the experimental samples from their respective CT values. The standard curve equations are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Equation for standard curves obtained from designed primers for the quantification of our samples through qPCR.

<i>mcrA</i>	-0.31x + 10.47	R ² :0.996
<i>hdrA</i>	-0.32x + 10.52	R ² :0.995

Figure 22 shows the results for the initial and final inoculum of the target genes. Similar patterns and copy numbers were observed for both *hdrA* and *mcrA* genes in the system. Across all inoculum samples and time points, no significant changes in gene copy numbers were detected. However, the E3 inoculum exhibited lower gene copy numbers at both the initial and final sampling stages. These findings suggest that the copy numbers of *hdrA* and *mcrA* were stable over time, with both genes displaying comparable quantities.

Figure 22. Graph of results obtained through qPCR of initial and final inoculum in the system. Transformed CT to copies. Plotted are the different times in our systems.

Figure 23 illustrates the time evolution of *hdrA* and *mcrA* copy numbers in the bulk catholyte. Both genes showed a similar growth pattern, with comparable copy number values. In the early stages, gene copy numbers significantly increased from approximately 10^2 to 10^5 . Over time, the system displayed a stabilizing trend in gene copy numbers, however, perturbations proved to influence the gene expression, and therefore the copy numbers present in the bulk catholyte. For instance, a shutdown test between T26 and T39 led to a decrease in gene copy numbers. Following reinoculation at T41, the gene copy count was lower in the liquid phase but recovered rapidly, surpassing pre-shutdown levels within just seven days (T51). Other disturbances, such as a power outage at T58 (which halted voltage and heating) and reduced current density at T65 (from 10 A m^{-2} to 5 A m^{-2}), similarly impacted gene copy numbers.

These observations suggest that factors such as pH and voltage fluctuations can alter methanogen copy numbers in the catholyte. Nevertheless, the system demonstrated resilience, recovering within a few days once optimal conditions were restored.

Figure 23. Graph of results obtained through qPCR of catholyte bulk samples in the system. Transformed CT to copies. Plotted are the different times in our systems through July, August and September.

6 BEM Process Optimization

6.1 Improved CO₂ dissolution using hollow fiber membrane contactors and development of a gas-liquid separation system

6.1.1 Separation system construction and implementation

Membrane contactors are unsuitable for operation with microbes-containing liquids, since biofilm-forming microorganisms can colonize the hollow fibers and clog the pores, thereby reducing the active surface area of the contactors. To address this issue, a gas-liquid separation unit, referred to as a 'settler,' was designed. The assembly schematic is reported in Figure 24. This unit is essential for separating the produced methane from the electrolyte and sedimenting the biomass present in the influent electrolyte. The thickened biomass is recirculated to the BEM cells, while the clarified supernatant is pumped into the membrane contactors. Additionally, the settler functions as a “carbon storage” for the microbial biomass during non-operational periods of the membrane contactors. For the laboratory-scale settler, a total volume of 8 liters—comprising 6 liters of liquid volume and 2 liters of headspace—was determined based on the expected CO₂ removal rates at a current density of 10 A/m² for the three BEM units. This design aims to retain enough dissolved CO₂ to provide the necessary substrate for a 72-hour period (weekend).

Figure 24. Detailed assembly diagram of the settler with an 8-liter volume capacity.

6.2 Electrochemical characterization

After 61 days of operation, Linear Sweep Voltammetry (LSV) was performed on all three BEM reactors at a scan rate of 1 mV/s, with a cathodic potential ranging from -0.5 V vs. Ag/AgCl to -1.50 V vs. Ag/AgCl. A wide cathodic potential window was chosen for this preliminary test to identify the most suitable lower and upper limits for subsequent polarization curve experiments.

Both electrochemical experiments were conducted with a portable potentiostat (SP-150, BioLogic, France) using a three-electrode setup. The cathode functioned as the working electrode, the anode as the counter electrode, and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode was placed in the cathode chamber. During the tests, both circuits were pressurized at 200mbar using non-return valves, and the electrolytes were recirculated at a flow rate of 200 mL/min. The catholyte was maintained at 35°C, and no CO₂ was supplied during the tests.

The current values were normalized to the cathode surface area (j_C) and anode surface area (j_A) and plotted against the electrode potential (Figure 25). Analyzing the respective LSV curves at the cathode (Figure 25a), it revealed similar trends across all three BEM reactors. At approximately -0.80 V vs. Ag/AgCl, a small electro-reductive current density was observed, which increased gradually to a maximum of -80 A/m² at around -1.20 V vs. Ag/AgCl. All LSV measurements were terminated around -1.20 V vs. Ag/AgCl, short of the intended -1.50 V, due to anode limitations. The anode potential rose to 8.0 V (the last recorded value before the potentiostat reached its 10 V safety limit), which caused the system to halt (Figure 25b). When normalized by anodic surface area, current density values were two orders of magnitude higher than those at the cathode. This discrepancy is due to the anode surface area being almost 14 times smaller than that of the cathode, leading to high potentials at increased current densities and likely limiting the system's kinetics.

Figure 25. Linear Sweep Voltammetry (LSV) curves of the three BEM reactors, performed after 61 days of operation, reporting the cathode potential against current density normalized by cathode surface (a) and anode potentials against current densities normalized by both cathode and anode surface (b). The cathodic potentials range from -0.5 V to -1.50 V vs. Ag/AgCl, with a scan rate of 1 mV/s. The anode reached its potential limit at 8.0 V, causing the experiment to halt before the set cathode potential of -1.50 V could be reached. Current values are normalized respect to the cathode surface area and anode surface area.

The Polarization Curves were obtained using five sequential chronoamperometric steps of 60 minutes each with a 0.100 V amplitude, at different cathode potentials ranging from -0.80 V vs. Ag/AgCl to -1.20 V vs. Ag/AgCl (selected based on the results from the previously conducted LSVs). Before and after the polarization curves, Open Circuit Voltage (OCV) measurements (30 minutes each) of both anode and cathode potentials were performed to ensure that the electrode potentials, under conditions of no applied voltage, had not changed due to the characterization of the BEM reactors. The operational conditions applied were the same used to obtain the LSV curves. Each polarization curve took 5 hours to complete, during which time neither the pH nor the conductivity of the catholyte or anolyte changed significantly.

The current values were normalized to the cathode surface area and anode surface area and plotted against single electrode potential (Figure 26a and b) and cell voltage (Figure 26c).

Analysing the curves in Figure 26, it appears that current consumption of all three BEM reactors evolved linearly with the cell voltage.

During the last polarization curve step (-1.20 V vs Ag/AgCl) the cell voltage of R2 and R3 rose to 10.0 V, causing the potentiostat to stop. Therefore, the only reported current density value at -1.2 V vs. Ag/AgCl cathode potential belongs to R1 (Figure 26a). Unlike the results obtained in the LSVs (Figure 25a), in the polarization curves R2 and R3 exhibited higher electrical current at the same cathode potential than R1. This variability in the three BEM replicates is expected when working with a biocathode.

Figure 26b shows that the kinetics of the anodes got limited at a potential near 5.0 V for R1 and R3, and this limitation was reported at a 3.70 V potential for R2. It must be noted that such a difference, although unexpected in 3 abiotic anodes, can be associated with the fact that the electrodes used were not brand new, and they could have been subject to some change that altered their catalytic capacity.

These results reinforce the previously stated hypothesis, which suggested that the limiting factor of the system was the selected anode, or more specifically, its reduced surface area.

Figure 26. Polarization curves of the three individual BEM reactors, reporting current density normalized both by cathode surface and anode surface against cathode potential (a), anode potential (b) and cell voltage (c). The cathodic potentials steps range from -0.8V to -1.2 V vs. Ag/AgCl, with a 0.1 V amplitude.

6.3 Energy consumption and power density of the laboratory scale BEM reactors

The energy consumed (in watt-hours, *Wh*) can be calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Energy (Wh)} = \text{Power (W)} \times \text{Time (h)}$$

The power (in watts, *W*) consumed by the 3 BEM units operated at a current density of 10 A m⁻², corresponding to an average cell voltage of 3 V, is given by:

$$\text{Power (total)} = 3 \times (0.121 \text{ A} \times 3 \text{ V}) = 1.089 \text{ W}$$

The BEM units produced on average a total of 0.3 Liters of methane per day (24h) at 10 A m⁻². The energy consumption per liter of methane produced can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Energy consumed per liter of methane produced} = 1.089 \text{ W} / 0.3 \frac{\text{L}}{24\text{h}} = 87.12 \frac{\text{Wh}}{\text{L}}$$

The calculated energy consumption for methane production in the BEM laboratory-scale process is 87 Wh L⁻¹. In comparison, energy consumption for methane production ranges from 26 to 35 Wh L⁻¹ for pilot scale thermochemical methanation (electrolysis + Sabatier process), and 19 Wh L⁻¹ for biochemical methanogenesis (electrolysis + methanogenesis), also at pilot scale [11]. This result is noteworthy because, although the laboratory-scale process consumes 3-5 times more energy, its energy efficiency is already within the range of pilot-scale technologies.

Each BEM unit has a cathodic volume of 0.25 L, for a total cathodic volume of 0.75 L. By dividing the calculated total power of the BEM units by the total cathodic volume, it is possible to calculate the system power density:

$$\text{Power density} = 1.089 \text{ W} / 7.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 = 1.45 \frac{\text{kW}}{\text{m}^3}$$

The calculated power density of the laboratory BEM system is 1.45 kW per cubic meter of reactor. This value complies with the KPI of the project of a power density in the kW / m³ range.

6.4 Identification of the limiting electricity demand of the biocathode

Electricity demand, particularly the operative current density of biocathodes, is a key factor in e-methane production. It influences both the reducing power delivered to the biomass in the form of hydrogen and the alkalinization of the catholyte. As current density increases, the rate of H₂ production rises, leading to higher proton consumption in the catholyte and greater alkalinization. However, excessive alkalinization can inhibit methanogenic activity, thereby disrupting CH₄ production.

To investigate the relationship between current density and pH changes in the electrolytes, three BEM units were operated galvanostatically at five constant current densities (10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 A/m²), normalized to the cathode surface area, over a seven-hour period. The highest current density (30 A/m²) was applied for only four hours due to rapid catholyte alkalinization at that level.

During the experiments, the anode and cathode circuits were pressurized at 200 mbar using non-return valves, and the electrolytes were recirculated at a flow rate of 200 mL/min. The catholyte was maintained at 35°C, and no CO₂ was supplied to prevent pH reduction. Hourly measurements included pH evolution in the anodic and cathodic compartments, dissolved CO₂ concentration in the catholyte, and the potential of each BEM unit component.

Figure 27 reports the pH increases in the catholyte and the dissolved CO₂ consumption in the catholyte relative to the current density applied at the biocathode. The pH variation at the cathode followed an exponential behaviour, starting from below 1 ΔpH day⁻¹ at 10 A m⁻² and reaching a 4.50 ± 0.72 ΔpH day⁻¹ at 30 A m⁻². Consequently, as current density increases, the rate of dissolved CO₂ consumption increase linearly. This is likely due to the higher H₂ evolution rates, which enhance CO₂ conversion and, consequently, methane production.

Higher operative current densities also lead to increased cell voltage, as shown in Table 2, and higher power density, as illustrated in Figure 28. The rise in cell voltage is primarily attributed to increased anode potentials and cell overpotentials. As current density increases from 10 to 30 A m⁻², the anode potential rises by 1.16 V, while cell overpotentials increase by 0.55 V, likely due to greater liquid resistance between the electrodes and separator overpotential. In contrast, the cathode potential increases only modestly, by approximately 0.11 V. These findings align with the results from Section 6.2, confirming that the anode is the limiting component in the BEM system.

Based on the overall results, a current density of 20 A m⁻² is the optimal choice for operating the scaled-up BEM plant. This current density is below the threshold where exponential catholyte alkalinization begins, allowing for stable pH control within the system. However, operating at this current density results in an increase in cell voltage by 0.8 V, primarily due to a 0.6 V rise in anode overpotential and a 0.2 V rise in cell overpotential compared to operation at 10 A m⁻².

Figure 27. Variation of pH evolution and consumption of dissolved CO₂ (mg L⁻¹) in the catholyte against current density normalized by cathode surface area.

Table 4. Average potentials of anode and cathode, cell voltage and the overpotential associated with the separator measured at different current densities.

Current density (A m ⁻²)	Anode potential (V)	Cathode potential (V)	Cell voltage (V)	Cell overpotential (V)
10	2.01 ± 0.07	-1.06 ± 0.05	3.34 ± 0.06	0.27 ± 0.04
15	2.30 ± 0.11	-1.06 ± 0.06	3.74 ± 0.12	0.38 ± 0.07
20	2.57 ± 0.10	-1.10 ± 0.06	4.14 ± 0.12	0.48 ± 0.09
25	2.80 ± 0.11	-1.13 ± 0.06	4.59 ± 0.09	0.66 ± 0.07
30	3.17 ± 0.13	-1.17 ± 0.06	5.17 ± 0.15	0.82 ± 0.06

Figure 28. Trend of the BEM system power density at increased operative current densities.

7 Conclusions

In tasks 3.1 and 3.2, a comprehensive investigation into the design, material selection, and performance optimization of bioelectrochemical methanation (BEM) reactors was conducted to support the development of the scaled-up pilot plant.

A promising 3D-structured stainless steel cathodic electrode material was identified as suitable for biocathode development through a comparative study of various cathodic electrode materials. Additionally, a suitable membrane contactor for CO₂ solubilization in the pilot plant was successfully selected and tested, and the design of a settler was completed. Three double-chamber BEM reactors were constructed, and a comprehensive control system was implemented, including pH control, temperature regulation, electrode potential monitoring, and gas composition and production analysis.

Long-term experiments were carried out to evaluate the performance of biocathodes, with a particular focus on pH and conductivity evolution, ion crossover, electrochemical potentials, and methane production. The study included the evaluation of different anode electrode materials and ion exchange membranes, as well as the monitoring of methanogenic gene expression via qPCR analysis, which highlighted the resilience of the microbial community to perturbations.

Electrical tests helped in characterizing the kinetics of the BEM reactors, optimizing current demand, and assessing energy consumption and power density. Overall, the findings of this study provide valuable insights for the design and operation of the pilot plant and significantly contribute to achieving the objectives of tasks 3.3 and 3.4, specifically objectives O3.3, O3.4, and O3.5. The successful outcomes of the laboratory-scale tests provide a solid foundation for scaling up bioelectrochemical methanation technology to pilot scale, facilitating efficient CO₂ utilization and methane production in line with project goals.

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9 Annex 1

Table 5. Composition of the catholyte mineral medium

Component	Amount	
Macronutrients		
<i>Na₂HPO₄ x 12H₂O</i>	11.7	g/L
<i>KH₂PO₄</i>	2.54	g/L
<i>NH₄Cl</i>	0.53	g/L
<i>Na₂SO₄</i>	0.1	g/L
<i>KCl</i>	0.052	g/L
<i>CaCl₂ x 2H₂O</i>	0.01	g/L
<i>MgCl₂ x 6H₂O</i>	0.72	g/L
<i>Trace elements solution</i>	1	mL/L
<i>Wolfe Vitamin Solution (1000x)</i>	1	mL/L
Trace element solution		
<i>NTA (Nitrilotriacetic acid)</i>	1.5	g/L
<i>MgSO₄ x 7H₂O</i>	3	g/L
<i>MnSO₄ x H₂O</i>	0.5	g/L
<i>NaCl</i>	1	g/L
<i>FeSO₄ x 7H₂O</i>	0.1	g/L
<i>ZnCl₂</i>	0.13	g/L
<i>CaCl₂ x 2H₂O</i>	0.1	g/L
<i>CoCl₂ x 6H₂O</i>	0.1	g/L
<i>CuSO₄ x 5H₂O</i>	0.01	g/L
<i>AlK(SO₄)₂ x 12H₂O</i>	0.01	g/L
<i>H₃BO₃</i>	0.01	g/L
<i>Na₂MoO₄ x 2 H₂O</i>	0.025	g/L
<i>NiCl₂ x 6 H₂O</i>	0.024	g/L
<i>Na₂WO₄ x 2 H₂O</i>	0.025	g/L
Wolfe Vitamin Solution (1000x)		
<i>Biotin (vit H)</i>	2	mg/L
<i>Folic acid (vit B9)</i>	2	mg/L
<i>Pyridoxine-HCl (vit B6)</i>	10	mg/L
<i>Riboflavin (vit B2)</i>	5	mg/L
<i>Thiamin-HCl (vit B1)</i>	5	mg/L
<i>Nicotinic acid (vit PP)</i>	5	mg/L
<i>Pantothenic acid or D(+)-Calcium-Pantothenate (vit B5)</i>	5	mg/L
<i>Cyanocobalamin (vit B12)</i>	0.1	mg/L
<i>p-aminobenzoic acid (vit B10)</i>	5	mg/L
<i>Thioctic acid (alfa-lipoic acid)</i>	5	mg/L